

Titrimetric Determination of Iron(III) with DCTA

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Iron(III) has been determined alone as well as in the presence of various ions by titrating with 1,2-diaminocyclohexanetetraacetic acid using alizarin red S and thioglycollic acid as indicators at pH 1.75-3.25 and 6.85-7.50 respectively. The method has been extended to the determination of iron(III) in its mixture with lead(II) as well as in haemetite, lime stone and cement.

CERTAIN attempts have already been made to determine iron(III) with 1, 2-diaminocyclohexanetetraacetic acid (DCTA) in strongly acidic medium¹⁻⁶. In the present communication, it has been determined alone as well as in the presence of various ions, in its mixture with lead and in haemetite, lime stone and cement by direct titration with DCTA using alizarin red S and thioglycollic acid as indicators in pH range 1.75-3.25 and 6.85-7.50 respectively.

Experimental

Reagents—DCTA (Koch-Light), alizarin red S (BDH), thioglycollic acid (E. Merck), iron(III) nitrate (BDH, AnalaR), haemetite (Dhanota-Dhancholi, Haryana, India), lime stone (Morni Hills, Haryana, India) and cement were used as such. All the other chemicals used were of guaranteed purity. Double distilled water was used in all the manipulations.

Solutions—The solutions of DCTA (0.005-0.05 M), iron(III) nitrate (0.005 M), haemetite (0.5750 g/litre), lime stone (7.2500 g/litre) and cement (6.5100 g/litre) were prepared and standardized or the iron content estimated by the reported methods^{4,7}.

Titrimetric determination using thioglycollic acid indicator—Iron(III) nitrate (0.5-5.0 ml) was reduced with calculated amount of ascorbic acid and then diluted with water (20-25 ml). Pyridine (2-3 ml) and thioglycollic acid (5 drops of 5% ethanolic solution) were added to it before titrating with standard DCTA solution to an abrupt colour change from violet to light yellow.

Titrimetric determination using alizarin red S indicator—An aliquot of iron(III) nitrate (0.5-5.0 ml), water (20-25 ml) and alizarin red S (3-4 drops of 0.2% aqueous solution) were titrated against standard DCTA solution after adjusting the pH to 1.75-3.25 either with sodium acetate and hydrochloric acid buffer (~5 ml) or by adding water and/or glacial acetic acid, if and when required. The end point was marked by a sharp colour change from greenish brown to light yellow.

An aliquot of solutions of iron(III) nitrate and aluminium(III) sulphate was treated with sodium thiosulphate (~5 ml of 5% solution), diluted with water (20-25 ml) and boiled free of sulphur dioxide. The contents were heated with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid to destroy the unconsumed sodium thiosulphate and also to reoxidize iron(II) formed, if any. The solution was cooled, neutralized with ammonia and titrated with DCTA using alizarin red S indicator after adjusting the pH.

An aliquot of the solution of lime stone, cement or haemetite (2-10 ml) was treated with DCTA using alizarin red S as indicator according to the above procedure after the removal of aluminium(III) in case of lime stone and cement.

The titrations were repeated at least five times at each concentration level.

Results and Discussion

DCTA reacts with iron(III) in 1 : 1 molar ratio under the experimental conditions. There is no dragging of the indicator colour near the end point. However, the addition of 2-3 drops of thioglycollic acid near the end point facilitates its detection more correctly. These titrations are simple, quick, reversible and quantitative, and are satisfactorily carried out in the temperature range 26-60°. As little as 0.15 mg of iron(III) is determined quantitatively in 25 ml solution in presence of 100-times excess of lithium, sodium, potassium, ammonium, chloride, nitrate and sulphate ions.

The behaviour of certain other foreign ions is different in case of these indicators probably due to the marked difference in the pH ranges at which the indicators are employed. Interfering effect of the metal ions depends principally on the difference in conditional stability constants of the various metal ions present in the solution. Thus in titrations using alizarin red S as indicator, 100-times excess of strontium and magnesium, 10-times excess of silver and 17-times excess of calcium ions is tolerable. Even 100-times excess of barium and 25-fold excess

of mercury(II) do not interfere in the pH range 1.75-1.78 and 1.75-2.50 respectively. However, only equimolar amounts are tolerable if pH lies in the range 1.78-3.25 and 2.50-3.50 respectively. Chromium(III) chloride does not interfere in the detection of end point if its amount present is less than 20 mg per 25 ml of the solution. In case of thioglycollic acid as an indicator, the titrations are possible in the presence of equimolar amounts of aluminium(III), strontium(II), barium(II), and oxalate, 10-times excess of sulphide, 2-times excess of phosphate, and 100-times excess of fluoride.

Lead(II), copper(II), zinc, cadmium and thorium (IV) interfere in the titrations using alizarin red S as indicator and the amount of DCTA consumed is exactly the one required for the sum of the amounts of these ions and iron(III), suggesting that these ions react with DCTA in 1:1 molar ratio under these conditions. Sulphide, phosphate, fluoride and oxalate ions interfere because of the formation of stable complexes with iron(III) in acidic medium. When thioglycollic acid is used as indicator, magnesium(II), calcium(II), mercury(II), lead(II), copper(II), zinc, cadmium, silver, chromium(III) and thorium(IV) interfere even when present in small amounts but the reaction of these ions with DCTA is not quantitative. Lanthanum(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), and thiosulphate ions interfere in these titrations using either of the indicators.

Calcium(II) and mercury(II) are masked with 2.5% potassium fluoride and 1% potassium iodide respectively. Lead(II) is removed by precipitating it out with 0.5 M sulphuric acid. The interference of

aluminium(III) salts is removed by hydrolysis with sodium thiosulphate in presence of mineral acids

Thiosulphate does not precipitate iron(III) but merely reduces it to iron(II). Other constituents of lime stone, cement and haemetite do not interfere in the titrations. Iron is thus estimated in these substances within $\pm 0.25\%$ error.

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